

Impact of stochastic fluctuations on proton beams under space-charge effects

Phil S. Yoon

^a Fermi National Accelerator Laboratory, Batavia, IL 60510, U.S.A.

^b Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Rochester, Rochester, NY 14620, U.S.A.

Abstract

Transient electric-current fluctuations arising from power supplies can be translated into magnetic-field perturbations during particle-accelerator operations. As speculated over the past decades, it is probable such inevitable machine imperfection leads to emittance growths, beam-halo formation, and consequential beam losses. With robust experimental evidence of transient coloured noise and its real-time Fast-Fourier-Transform analysis, the ripple currents were modelled on the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process via parameterisation. For investigating the conjectured effects on intense beams, the first-ever, data-driven stochastic noise model—equipped with the wide-spectrum noise generator and a suite of beam-diagnostic calculations—was formulated with massive realism; i.e., tracking a huge number of macroparticles propagating through focusing channels in the face of power-supply noise and space charge. With uniform charge-density distributions at injection, the power-supply ripples and collective effects due to space charge conspire to yield fractional growths of r.m.s. emittances as large as $8 \sim 9 \%$ in both transverse planes over a 2.2-ms period, prior to accelerating beams. It was thus concluded that fluctuating power-supply currents, when coupled to space charge and impinging upon intense proton beams, can substantially escalate the insidious process of degrading beam properties during the full injection period. This article concerns the systematised methodology of a hybrid of empirical datasets and a numerical model created and developed for quantitatively assessing the impact of frequency-dependent noise on beams and attendant ramifications engendered in its space-charge-dominated sphere.

Keywords: accelerator physics; accelerator modelling; beam injection; Brownian motion; charged-particle beams; fluctuation phenomena; Langevin method; nonlinear dynamics; power supply; space charge; stochastic noise; synchrotrons

1. INTRODUCTION

Subtle and transient fluctuations are inevitable and ubiquitous in a wide variety of phenomena in nature: *e.g.*, operation of particle accelerators, climate changes, colloid chemistry, stellar dynamics to name a few. To start out, an ensemble of charged particles is defined as *the system*, and all the beamline components—such as radio-frequency (RF) cavities, magnets, power supplies, beam-diagnostic devices, etc—are designed for accelerating, guiding, and diagnosing particle beams as *the surroundings* that interact closely with the system. These charged-particle beams (hereafter *the beams*) identify the surroundings of beamline components as sources of transient noise (Figure 1). Intrinsic to particle accelerators of all types is external noise caused by such unavoidable machine imperfections, or environmental disturbances of terrestrial, anthropogenic, or electric origin: *e.g.*, seismic activities, ground vibration motions, traffic noise on surface

ground in the vicinity, and ripple currents from power supplies.

Figure 1 | The system and the surroundings defined for modelling a particle-accelerator system.

Motivated by prior findings from simplified, theoretical models of coloured noise[1, 2], the following idea was proposed: The adverse influence of fluctuating electric currents (hereafter

Figure 2 | Block diagram illustrating the multistage approach taken to modelling the influence of power-supply noise on intense proton beams under the influence of space-charge forces.

the ripples) originating from the magnet’s power supplies accounts possibly for the conspicuous beam losses plaguing during the injection period of the Booster synchrotron (hereafter *the Booster*)[3]. This pernicious occurrence of sapping proton beams of their intensities raised serious concerns for the fixed-target experiments relying upon sorely needed intense proton beams sourced from the Booster[4, 5]. To this end, this stochastic noise model has been developed to investigate this uncanny phenomenon, of which emergence was speculated to be from potential ripples of power supplies of the low- γ synchrotron.

This article is organised in the actual sequence of how this investigation empowered by modelling of hybrid type has progressed.

2. MODELLING METHODOLOGY

The growing and pressing need to investigate the harmful effects, which the ripples may produce on beams, had left strong motivation for creating a stochastic noise model with massive realism. At first, a potent and efficient numerical algorithm was developed; the new algorithm embedding a Box-Muller-like transformation was designed to generate a wide spectrum of parameterised stochastic noise by harnessing the O-U process[7–9](sec. 5.2). This new noise module, in turn, dovetails with the framework of the existing Objective Ring Beam Injection and Tracking (ORBIT) simulation code for tracking charged-particle beams in 6-D phase space[10]. Prior to measuring and

characterising the ripples, we simulated such degrading influences on beams propagating through periodic focusing channels under space-charge effects by adding the O-U noise with differing strengths. Our intellectual interest was sparked and stimulated by the results from the preliminary model corroborating the potential adverse effects of external fluctuations on beams. Moreover, the preliminary finding is consistent with the earlier ones from a cohort of theorists who studied collective space-charge modes coupled with dynamic noise[1, 2]. With assurance about strong correlations between power-supply noise, space charge, and beam losses, experimental methods were pursued to devise for measuring common- and differential-mode voltages and capturing miniscule transients in the power-supply currents. The real-time Fourier analysis of data sampled from each individual power supply verified the subsistence of time-dependent stochastic fluctuations transmissive through the magnet circuitry (Section 3.4). Moreover, equivalent-circuit simulations helped to bear out existent resonances around the magnet system. The method of computationally-efficient Fast-Fourier-Transform (FFT) was utilised to analyse the measured current ripples on the oscilloscope in real time. Based upon the FFT analysis, the stochastic parameterisation of the ripples was performed by means of matching the power-spectral densities (PSDs) between the measured ripples and the simulated noise[8]. By translating modelled O-U noise into induced magnetic-field undulations, tracking huge herds of macroparticles (simulation particles) was reiterated under the influence

of three dimensional (3-D) space-charge forces. The following Figure 2 and Figure 3 illustrate the multistage approach to modelling current ripples and their influence on beams. For parameterising the stochastic ripples, the experimental *signature space* mapped on to the stochastic *parameter space* (Figure 3); in this process, great care was taken to tune faithfully up the model on the data of the ripples.

Figure 3 | Mapping the experimental signature space on to the stochastic parameter space.

3. NOISE-MEASURING TECHNIQUES AND ANALYSES

This section is devoted to techniques of measuring and analysing transient coloured noise echoing around the accelerator’s power system.

3.1. Common- and Differential-Mode Noise

Sampling 15-Hz current waveforms on the main bus line (Figure 4) and measuring common-mode (CM) and differential-mode (DM) voltages together were conducted at each respective units of gradient-magnet power supply (hereafter *the power supply*, or *GMPS*) (Figure 5 and Figure 6). A series of measurements confirmed that ripple currents and CM voltages have been consistently detected and thus are not of seasonal behaviour appearing at each power-supply unit (Supplementary Figure 1).

Figure 4 | Current waveform of 15 Hz taken at GMPS [1]. Its frequency and period are displayed in the background.

Figure 5 | A tandem of the power-supply units stand side by side in the East Booster Gallery. The waveforms of both V_{+G} and V_{-G} signals (Figure 6) were sampled directly from the power-supply control rack seen on the front chassis.

Figure 6 | Flow paths of common- and differential-mode currents are illustrated. The DC output of the power supply was filtered with a L - C network with a 15-Hz low-pass filter in order to smooth the differential-mode sawtooth waveforms at all power-supply units. On the other hand, the waveforms of CM voltage V_{CM} are noticeably fast fluctuating, thereby inducing additional current fluctuations in the system.

CM and DM voltages were computed on a digital oscilloscope (Agilent 54622A) in *real time* as follows:

$$\begin{cases} V_{CM} = V_{+G} + V_{-G} \\ V_{DM} = V_{+G} - V_{-G} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

A campaign of measurements has revealed that the two root causes of the common-mode noise arising from each power-supply unit are thus: (1) additional phase lags ΔX in V_{+G} and V_{-G} and (2) potential differentials between V_{+G} and \tilde{V}_{-G} . When V_{+G} and V_{-G} are added on the scope in a point-by-point fashion, they do not cancel out each other. Rather, the ripples on each waveform add up and the common-mode voltage stands out. The potential differentials and the phase lags measured at individual power-supply units are summarised in Table 1. As found, the fractional potential differential of GMPS [2] is amongst the greatest.

Table 1 | Differentials of voltage amplitudes (ΔV) and phase lags (ΔX) between V_{+G} and V_{-G} at each respective GMPS unit.

GMPS [No.]	V_{+G} (V)	V_{-G} (V)	$ \Delta V/V_{+G} $	ΔX (ms)
GMPS [1]	1.577	1.905	20.8 %	0.6
GMPS [2]	3.232	1.699	47.4 %	4.0
GMPS [3]	1.598	1.740	8.90 %	1.4
GMPS [4]	1.581	1.743	10.2 %	4.6

3.2. Power Spectral Density: FFT Analysis

Evidencing the existence of CM voltages and current ripples rising above baseline current signals at the four power supplies are Fourier-analysed on the fly.

3.3. Stochastic Parameter Estimation

The autocorrelation time τ_{ac} can be thought of as a memory span, or a measure of the dependency on a single stochastic value at two distinct times (t and t'). In this subsection, characterising the measured current fluctuations were accomplished by determining a set of three stochastic quantities that follows:

- (1) **time step Δt** : The Booster's entire magnet system is divided into four quadrants, each of which constitutes a string of 24 magnets in series connection. And each of the four power-supply units drives its corresponding quadrant. Current fluctuations $\Delta I/I$ stemming from each power-supply are transmissible through a string of magnets contained in each quadrant. As such, all of the 24 magnets undergo the same amount of ripple currents at an interval of the time step. Thus, we made a choice of the time step, or noise-sampling rate equivalent to one-revolution period ($T_0 = 2.2 \mu s$) at an injection energy of 400 MeV.
- (2) **autocorrelation time τ_{ac}** : On the basis of direct current measurements from a main bus line, the ripples are repeated above the baseline current, or reference current at a steady interval (Figure 7). Thus, a span of $1.5 \sim 1.7$ ms is elected to be the proper autocorrelation time for current fluctuations from the power supplies.
- (3) **noise strength \mathcal{A}** : Based upon the ripple currents ΔI rising above a linear-ramp segment of a sinusoidal current waveform (Figure 7), the r.m.s. value of fractional current fluctuations $\Delta I/I|_{rms}$ is measured to be on the order of 10^{-4} . For validating purposes, histograms of the O-U noise at the nodes are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 7 | Shown on the scope display are ripples subsisting on a linear segment of a sinusoidal current waveform that were sampled directly from the magnet bus line.

Figure 8 | A total of four noise nodes, each representing its corresponding power supply, are inserted symmetrically within the Booster model. Histograms of the noise amplitudes generated at four random-noise nodes established within the model. The r.m.s. values of the noise amplitudes remain on the same order as those of measured noise strengths.

The pertinent FFT analysis of the acquired 15-Hz currents was performed over one-period range. The power spectral densities of the simulated O-U noise and the measured ripple currents were closely matched (Figure 9).

3.4. Equivalent-Circuit Model

Equivalent-circuit modelling has revealed the possibility of the existence of offending resonances that act as *noise amplifiers*, whilst reverberating through the magnet system. The SPICE (B2 SPICE A/D Version 4) model of one single *LC*-resonant cell is drawn in Figure 10[22, 23]. The results of AC analysis

(a) measured ripple currents

(b) simulated Ornstein-Uhlenbeck noise

Figure 9 | (a) Shown above are FFT impulses and a 15-Hz current waveform of one cycle; the horizontal scale is set to 167 Hz/div and the vertical scale to 20 dB/div. (b) The vertical scale is 10^{-1} /div to indicate power attenuation from unity.

of the equivalent circuits are shown in Figure 11. The current is peaked at 15 Hz and a cluster of minor peaks are accompanied in a few kHz range. Our interpretation is that those offending resonances in the higher frequency band (> 15 Hz) can amplify the power-supply noise, when the frequencies of power-supply noise coincide with those of resonances. Consequently, the existent resonances could accentuate the formation of beam halos, leading to pronounced beam losses incurred throughout the full injection cycle.

F-Magnet

(a) Focusing Magnet

D-Magnet

(b) Defocusing Magnet

Choke

(c) Choke

Figure 10 | One focusing magnet, one defocusing magnet, and one choke constitute each magnet cell of the equivalent-circuit model.

4. NOISE CLASSIFICATION AND CHARACTERISATION

In the preceding section, the noise-measuring techniques have confirmed and brought robust evidence for the presence of frequency-dependent stochastic noise arising from the power system. This stochastic noise model takes the power-supply ripples as exter-

Figure 11 | Currents in frequency domain generated by SPICE simulations; a single power supply drives currents flowing through a string of 12 magnet cells. Progressing from top to bottom, the traces correspond to magnet cell [1] through [12].

nal fluctuations impinging upon proton beams sourced from the Booster (Figure 1).

4.1. External Noise and Electromagnetic Interferences

The ripples are considered *indeterministic*, *stochastic*, or *aperiodic* in the sense that the occurrence of such current fluctuations never repeat themselves in an exact manner. Conductive electromagnetic interference (EMI) noise—such as common-mode and differential-mode noise—is usually several orders of magnitude more copious than the radiative EMI, and thus can be more damaging to the system. Given impedance $Z(\omega)$ as a function of frequency ω , fluctuations in common-mode voltage V_{CM} induce common-mode currents I_{CM} , in addition to the inherent ripples from sudden change in electric potential. Such EMI problems can worsen and give rise to larger current fluctuations, or common-mode currents, thus causing severe system damage.

5. GENERATING FREQUENCY-DEPENDENT STOCHASTIC NOISE

This section concerns how to devise and implement the numerical algorithm for generating time- and frequency-dependent stochastic noise in the new noise module.

5.1. Stochastic Properties

Langevin's Equation governs the O-U process. For basing the model of current ripples on the O-U process, Langevin-like equation has been formulated and solved. One can extract more statistical properties of the O-U process beyond the posterior properties by solving the convenient first-degree, first-order linear Langevin-like equation. Let us first consider the first-order SDE in the form of LE.

$$\dot{\xi}(t) = f(\xi) + \eta(t) \quad (2)$$

Here $\eta(t)$ is non-white Gaussian noise with its autocorrelation function C_η :

$$C_\eta(t, t') = \langle \eta(t)\eta(t') \rangle = \frac{\mathcal{A}}{2\omega_{ac}} \exp(-\omega_{ac}|t - t'|) \quad (3)$$

LE governs non-white noise $\eta(t)$ with a white-noise driving force of $\mathcal{L}(t)$:

$$\dot{\eta}(t) + \omega_{ac}\eta(t) = \mathcal{L}(t) \quad (4)$$

The autocorrelation function $C_{\mathcal{L}}$ is δ -correlated with a strength \mathcal{A} :

$$C_{\mathcal{L}}(t, t') = \langle \mathcal{L}(t)\mathcal{L}(t') \rangle = \mathcal{A}\delta(t - t') \quad (5)$$

Ornstein and Uhlenbeck [8], Doob [19], and van Kampen [9] used the integration method to determine the statistical properties of non-white noise, or coloured noise from LE. We, on the other hand, solved LE as a first-order differential equation. Hence, the following solution to LE was worked out:

$$\eta(t) = \eta(0)\exp(-\omega_{ac}t) + \int_0^t ds \cdot \exp(-\omega_{ac}(t-s))\mathcal{L}(s) \quad (6)$$

The stochastic process at the next time step $t + \Delta t$ can be found from Eqn. (6):

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(t + \Delta t) &= \eta(0)\exp(-\omega_{ac}(t + \Delta t)) + \int_0^{t + \Delta t} ds \exp(-\omega_{ac}(t + \Delta t - s))\mathcal{L}(s) \\ &= \eta(t)\exp(-\omega_{ac}\Delta t) + \underbrace{\int_t^{t + \Delta t} ds \exp(-\omega_{ac}(t + \Delta t - s))\mathcal{L}(s)}_{H(t, t + \Delta t)} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

By transforming the variables of integration, one can arrive at

$$\begin{aligned} H(0, \Delta t) &= \int_0^{\Delta t} d\tilde{s} \cdot \exp(-\omega_{ac}(\Delta t - \tilde{s})) \mathcal{L}(\tilde{s} + t) \\ &= \exp(-\omega_{ac}\Delta t) \int_0^{\Delta t} d\tilde{s} \cdot \exp(\omega_{ac}\tilde{s}) \mathcal{L}(\tilde{s} + t) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Further, one can derive the following by squaring Eqn. (8):

$$\begin{aligned} \{H(0, \Delta t)\}^2 &= \exp(-2\omega_{ac}\Delta t) \int_0^{\Delta t} \int_0^{\Delta t} d\tilde{s} d\tilde{s}' \exp(\omega_{ac}(\tilde{s} + \tilde{s}')) \mathcal{L}(\tilde{s} + t) \mathcal{L}(\tilde{s}' + t) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The statistical properties of a stochastic variable can be studied by calculating various moments. Accordingly, the first and the second central moments were calculated by averaging Eqns. (8) and (9) over an ensemble of particles. For zero-mean Gaussian, the 1st moment vanishes: $\langle H(0, \Delta t) \rangle = 0$

Cognisant of the fact that the O-U process is a stationary process, the 2nd moments boil down to the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \{H(0, \Delta t)\}^2 \rangle &= \exp(-2\omega_{ac}\Delta t) \int_0^{\Delta t} \int_0^{\Delta t} d\tilde{s} d\tilde{s}' \exp(\omega_{ac}(\tilde{s} + \tilde{s}')) \langle \mathcal{L}(\tilde{s}) \mathcal{L}(\tilde{s}') \rangle \\ &= \mathcal{A} \exp(-2\omega_{ac}\Delta t) \int_0^{\Delta t} d\tilde{s} \exp(2\omega_{ac}\tilde{s}) \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{A}}{2\omega_{ac}} \{1 - \exp(-2\omega_{ac}\Delta t)\} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The second moments of $H(0, \Delta t)$ can be expanded in a closed form as in Eqn. (11).

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \{H(0, \Delta t)\}^2 \rangle &= \frac{\mathcal{A}}{2\omega_{ac}} \left\{ 1 - \exp(-2\omega_{ac}\Delta t) \right\} \\ &= \mathcal{A}\Delta t \left[1 - R_t + \frac{2}{3}R_t^2 - \frac{1}{3}R_t^3 + \dots \right], \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

with R_t being $\omega_{ac}\Delta t$. What determines the $\langle H^2 \rangle$ is $\omega_{ac}\Delta t$ that is time step Δt in units of autocorrelation time τ_{ac} , not autocorrelation time, or time step by itself. This noise module was inherently designed to generate the O-U stochastic noise $\eta(t)$ to be applied to macroparticles in the form of magnetic-field

perturbations: *autocorrelation time* τ_{ac} , *time step* Δt , and *noise strength* \mathcal{A} .

5.2. Box-Muller-Like Transformation

The Box-Muller transformation [7, 21] is intrinsically for generating independent Gaussian white noise—which is a limiting case of physical noise—from independent uniform random deviates. In order to generate exponentially-driven Gaussian stochastic noise, an exponential factor $\exp(-\omega\Delta t)$ is first multiplied by the stochastic noise $\eta(t)$ at present time t . Then, an r.m.s. value of $H(0, \Delta t)$ is added to compute the noise at the next time step $t + \Delta t$.

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(t + \Delta t) &= \exp(-\omega\Delta t)\eta(t) + C_W \sqrt{\langle H(t, t + \Delta t)^2 \rangle} \\ &= \exp(-\omega\Delta t)\eta(t) + C_W \sqrt{\langle H(0, \Delta t)^2 \rangle}, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where C_W denotes random deviates from a rectangular distribution (or white noise). What Eqn. (12) implies is that generating $\eta(t + \Delta t)$ requires one to know $\eta(t)$ only. This takes advantage of the powerful *Markov property* belonging to the O-U process in numerical calculations. Upon providing with stochastic parameters, the variant of the Box-Muller transformation is capable of generating a wide spectrum of stochastic noise in both time and frequency domains: *coloured noise*, *non-white noise*, *off-white noise*, *white noise*, etc. Graphed in Supplementary Figure 6 are the sample paths of noise with differing stochastic parameters. The time step is fixed at one revolution period of circulating proton beams at the Booster's injection energy. As can be seen from Supplementary Figure 6, the autocorrelation time governs the pattern of sample path. It is, therefore, evident that the pattern of all sample paths are *aperiodic*.

5.3. Application of Stochastic Noise to Macroparticles

This noise model takes in measurements of current ripples translating linearly into magnetic-field undulations, as in Eqn. (13).

$$\tilde{\mathbf{K}}_{imag} = \mathbf{K}_{imag} + \left| \Delta \mathbf{K}_{imag} \right| = \mathbf{K}_{imag} \cdot \left(1 + \left| \Delta \mathbf{K}_{imag} \right| / \mathbf{K}_{imag} \right), \quad (13)$$

where the subscript *imag* denotes magnet index for differentiating between individual main dipole magnets. In order to distinguish field fluctuations at each type of magnet (focusing, or defocusing), \mathbf{K}_{imag} is factored out, and the amount of

field variation $\Delta \mathbf{K}_{imag}$ is normalised by \mathbf{K}_{imag} as a perturbation term.

6. BEAM TRACKING AND DIAGNOSIS

6.1. Simulation Parameters

A comprehensive set of machine parameters for the Booster ring at an injection energy is summed up in Table 2. In addition, key parameters of ORBIT-FERMI¹ including space-charge calculations are abstracted in Table 3. Prior to tracking, injecting into the Booster ring a round beam with axisymmetry and uniform charge distributions ensures that one can solely investigate the noise-induced phenomena under the full space-charge conditions alone.

6.2. Moments

We present how various measures of beam diagnosis are defined and computed in this stochastic noise model. Moments are defined to characterise probability distributions of a beam, or macroparticles. Since it is essential to consider beam motions, the ORBIT-FERMI simulations employ central moments in transverse planes ($\langle x \rangle$ and $\langle y \rangle$) at the onset:

$$\begin{cases} \Delta x_r = x_r - \langle x_r \rangle \\ \Delta y_r = y_r - \langle y_r \rangle, \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where $x_r(z)$ and $y_r(z)$ denote real-space coordinates. Because of vanishing central-moment calculations, beam centroids themselves ($\langle x \rangle$ and $\langle y \rangle$) are used for the 1st-moment calculations. It is assumed that the density profiles of an actual beam in transverse planes are *bi-Gaussian*. Upon injection of a herd of macroparticles of bi-Gaussian distribution, one can compute the 2nd-moments for calculating r.m.s. beam sizes (σ_x, σ_y):

$$\text{1st moments} \begin{cases} \langle x_r \rangle \\ \langle y_r \rangle \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

$$\text{2nd moments} \begin{cases} \sigma_x^2 = \langle (\Delta x_r)^2 \rangle \\ \sigma_y^2 = \langle (\Delta y_r)^2 \rangle \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

¹ The Fermilab version of ORBIT (hereafter *ORBIT-FERMI*) has been further developed by adding additional modules for studying some adverse effects that machine imperfections can have on beams in a space-charge dominated sphere.

Table 2 | Machine parameters for Fermilab's Booster at an injection energy.

ring radius, $\langle R \rangle$	75.47 (m)
ring circumference	474.2 (m)
injection kinetic energy	400 (MeV)
synchronous energy, E_s	1.328 (GeV)
Lorentz factor, β	0.7131
Lorentz factor, γ	1.426
revolution period, T_0	2.2 (μ s)
number of injection turns	11
full injection period	24.2 (μ s)
cycle time	66.7 (ms)
transition gamma, γ_{tr}	5.4696
momentum compaction factor, α_1	0.0172
phase-slip factor, $ \eta $	0.458
95 %, normalised, $\epsilon_{tr,95,n}$	12.0 (π -mm-mrad)
RF range	38.18 ~ 52.83 (MHz)
bare tunes, $v_{x0} \mid v_{y0}$	6.7 \mid 6.8
betatron frequency, $f_{\beta,x} \mid f_{\beta,y}$	318.2 \mid 363.6 (kHz)
synchrotron tune, Q_s	1.147×10^{-3}
synchrotron frequency, Ω_s	3.28 (kHz)
synchrotron period, T_s	305 (μ s)
r.m.s. bunch length, σ_z	1.0 (m)
longitudinal beta function, β_z	3.0×10^4 (m)
longitudinal emittance, ϵ_L	0.25 (eV-s)
batch intensity	5.04×10^{12}
average beam current (at injection)	420 (mA)
effective beam radius, r_{eff}	0.0325 (m)
bunching factor, B_f	~ 0.4
space-charge tune shifts, $\Delta\nu$	- 0.4
$\Delta P/P_0 \Big _{max}$	± 0.15 %
σ_δ	3.0×10^{-4}
beta functions, $\beta_{x,max} \mid \beta_{y,max}$	33.7 \mid 20.5 (m)
dispersion functions,	3.2 \mid 0.0 (m)
$D_{x,max} \mid D_{y,max}$	
cell type	FOFDOOD
cell length	20.62 (m)
gradient magnets/cell	4
total gradient magnets	96
RF voltage at injection, $V_{rf,inj}$	205.0 (kV/Turn)
phase advance/cell	96 (deg)
defocusing bending radius, ρ_D	48.034100 (m)
focusing bending radius, ρ_F	40.847086 (m)

The r.m.s. beam sizes are important for space-charge study. Starting with the bi-Gaussian charge distribution $\rho(r)$, one can derive transverse space-charge force $F_{sc}(r)$, using Gauss' and Ampère's laws. The transverse r.m.s. beam sizes σ_r determine

Table 3 | Key simulation parameters (ORBIT-FERMI) for the Booster. LSC and TSC stand respectively for longitudinal and transverse space charge.

no. of injection turns	11
no. of max. macroparticles	330,000
harmonic number	84
beam kinetic energy	400.0 (MeV)
beam intensity (per RF bucket)	6.0×10^{10}
transverse beam distribution	bi-Gaussian
ring circumference	474.2 (m)
$\beta_{x,inj} \beta_{y,inj}$	6.274 19.312 (m)
$\alpha_{x,inj} \alpha_{y,inj}$	-0.122 0.024
$D_{x,0} D_{y,0}$	2.581 0.0 (m)
$x_{0,inj} y_{0,inj}$	0.0 0.0 (mm)
E_{offset}	0.0 (GeV)
$\Delta E/E_{kinetic}$	5.1×10^{-4}
$\epsilon_{x,rms,inj} \epsilon_{y,rms,inj}$	1.76 1.76 (π -mm-mrad)
RF voltage, V_{rf}	205.0 (kV/Turn)
R_{wall}/R_{beam} (for geometric factor)	2.0
LSC bin no.	32
TSC bin no.	64 x 64
smoothing parameter	$\sim 10^{-6}$
min. no. of particles/LSC bin	16
min. no. of particles/TSC bin	128
no. of total tracking turns	1,000

the range of linear transverse space-charge forces $F_{sc}(r)$ (Eqn. (17)):

$$\begin{cases} \rho(r) = \frac{Ne}{2\pi\sigma_r^2} \exp\left(-\frac{r^2}{2\sigma_r^2}\right) \\ \vec{F}_{sc}(r) = \frac{Ne^2}{2\pi\epsilon_0\gamma^2 r L_b} \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{r^2}{2\sigma_r^2}\right)\right) \hat{r} \\ r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}, \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

where N , e , ϵ_0 , σ_r , γ , r , and L_b denote the number of particles per length, unit charge, permittivity of vacuum, r.m.s. beam size, Lorentz factor, radial distance, and bunch length, respectively. The transverse space-charge forces grow linearly with transverse displacements (x , or y), and scale off ($\propto 1/r$) with displacements larger than $2\sigma_r$. According to the evolution of the 2nd-moment calculations, the r.m.s. beam sizes grow steadily without cease in the presence of the full space charge forces and the ripples. To understand the time evolution of r.m.s. beam sizes, or beam widths in transverse planes, the 2nd moments in real physical space are computed.

$$\begin{cases} x_r(z) = x_\beta(z) + D_x(z) \cdot \frac{\Delta p}{p_0} \\ y_r(z) = y_\beta(z) \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

In Eqn. (18), $x_\beta(z)$ and $y_\beta(z)$ denote betatron coordinates, and $D_{x0}(z)$ and p_0 respectively denote injection horizontal dispersion and design momentum. In a similar fashion, divergence angles are computed:

$$\begin{cases} x'_r(z) = x'_\beta(z) + D'_x(z) \cdot \frac{\Delta p}{p_0} \\ y'_r(z) = y'_\beta(z), \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

where $D'_x(z)$ denotes the slope of horizontal dispersion.

6.3. Emittances

Since the ORBIT-FERMI simulations employ the 2nd-order central moments for calculating r.m.s. emittances, a few measures were defined thus:

$$\begin{cases} \Delta p_x \equiv p_x - \langle p_x \rangle \\ \Delta p_y \equiv p_y - \langle p_y \rangle \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

For computing the 2nd-order central moments of each individual coordinate in the 6-dimensional space, column matrices $M_{2,x}$ and $M_{2,y}$ were constructed:

$$M_{2,x} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta x_\beta \\ \Delta x'_\beta \end{bmatrix} \quad M_{2,y} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta y_\beta \\ \Delta y'_\beta \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

With the column matrices M_2 above, 2×2 Σ -matrices were defined in subspaces of trace space: (x_β, x'_β) and (y_β, y'_β) . In each of Σ -matrices, the off-diagonal elements are associated with the correlation between positions and angles, or energy and RF phase.

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma(x_\beta, x'_\beta) &\equiv \langle M_{2,x_\beta} M_{2,x_\beta}^T \rangle \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \langle (\Delta x_\beta)^2 \rangle & \langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta x'_\beta \rangle \\ \langle \Delta x'_\beta \Delta x_\beta \rangle & \langle (\Delta x'_\beta)^2 \rangle \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

in which M^T denotes a transpose matrix of M . Using the 2×2 Σ -matrix, an *unnormalised r.m.s. emittance* can be defined as follows[25]:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{x,rms} &= \sqrt{\det \Sigma(x_\beta, x'_\beta)} \\ &= \sqrt{\langle (\Delta x_\beta)^2 \rangle \langle (\Delta x'_\beta)^2 \rangle - \underbrace{\langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta x'_\beta \rangle^2}_{\text{correlation term}}} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Transverse r.m.s. emittances are defined in $(x_\beta, p_x/p_0)$ and $(y_\beta, p_y/p_0)$ phase spaces, following the MAD[26] convention:

$$\Sigma(x_\beta, p_x) = \begin{bmatrix} \langle (\Delta x_\beta)^2 \rangle & \langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta p_x \rangle \\ \langle \Delta p_x \Delta x_\beta \rangle & \langle (\Delta p_x)^2 \rangle \end{bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{x,rms} &= \frac{1}{p_0} \sqrt{\det \Sigma(x_\beta, p_x)} \\ &= \frac{1}{\gamma\beta m_0 c} \sqrt{\langle (\Delta x_\beta)^2 \rangle \langle (\Delta p_x)^2 \rangle - \langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta p_x \rangle^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

in which the transverse momenta (p_x and p_y) are normalised by the design momentum p_0 . The Eqns. (21) through (25) apply likewise to vertical and longitudinal planes.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \epsilon_{x,n,rms} = (\beta\gamma)\epsilon_{x,rms} \\ = (\beta\gamma) \sqrt{\langle (\Delta x_\beta)^2 \rangle \cdot \langle (\Delta x'_\beta)^2 \rangle - \langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta x'_\beta \rangle^2} \\ = \frac{1}{m_0 c} \sqrt{\langle (\Delta x_\beta)^2 \rangle \langle (\Delta p_x)^2 \rangle - \langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta p_x \rangle^2} \\ \epsilon_{y,n,rms} = (\beta\gamma)\epsilon_{y,rms} \\ = (\beta\gamma) \sqrt{\langle (\Delta y_\beta)^2 \rangle \langle (\Delta y'_\beta)^2 \rangle - \langle \Delta y_\beta \Delta y'_\beta \rangle^2} \\ = \frac{1}{m_0 c} \sqrt{\langle (\Delta y)^2 \rangle \langle (\Delta p_y)^2 \rangle - \langle \Delta y \Delta p_y \rangle^2} \end{array} \right. \quad (26)$$

7. IMPACT OF ELECTRIC-CURRENT FLUCTUATIONS UNDER SPACE-CHARGE FORCES

Four random-noise nodes, provided with characteristic noise parameters, are inserted into the linear lattice of the Booster synchrotron. Macroparticles representing proton beams were tracked over 1,000 turns in the presence of full space charge forces². As shown in Figure 12, the time evolution of transverse r.m.s. emittances with the space-charge forces alone (blue) and with the O-U noise and the full space-charge forces (red). The beam intensity is 5.0×10^{12} protons per batch. To estimate the emittance growth rate prior to accelerating beams, the relative emittance growths ($\Delta\epsilon/\epsilon_0$) are calculated, starting from the final injection turn (the 11th turn) through 1,000 turns—this corresponds to the first 2.2 ms. The relative emittance growth ($\Delta\epsilon/\epsilon_0$) is about 7.5 % in the horizontal plane, and 9.3 % in the vertical plane. Simulated and tracked are a total of 330,000 macroparticles amassed by repeatedly injecting 30,000 macroparticles per injection turn. Upon inclusion of the O-U noise representing the ripples the beam-degrading progression

² In the present context, the full space charge is referred to as both transverse and longitudinal space charge, or 3-D space charge.

is set in development under space charge, thereby forming more noticeable beam halos. As a cross-check with the calculations of r.m.s. emittances, average actions (J_x and J_y) were computed at each tracking turn under the same conditions. For clear comparison, the r.m.s. emittances and average actions are overlaid in Figure 13. Calculating both r.m.s. emittances and actions manifests in such a good agreement that beam-degrading progression is considerably escalated. The time evolution of r.m.s. beam sizes in both transverse planes with space charge alone and with the ripples and space charge combined are illustrated in Figure 14. With the O-U noise added, the 2nd moments of the beams (beam size squared) grow faster than in the case for space charge alone as beams circulate. If one lowers the batch intensity by an order of one magnitude than the operational batch intensity under the same conditions (5×10^{11}), emittance growths induced by the ripples and space-charge effects combined are indistinguishable from those by space charge alone (Figure 15). This is a clear signature implying that only when the space-charge effects are substantial, the power-supply ripples exert considerable influence on the beams.

7.1. Couplings

On top of the primary calculations—r.m.s. emittances and average actions—we looked into the transverse couplings to better understand this noise-induced phenomenon. Computing the 2nd-order cross moment $\langle xy \rangle$ for each case is presented in Figure 18. A marginal amount of couplings are introduced when the full space-charge effects are present with no power-supply noise (Figure 18 (b)). When the noise is included alone in the absence of the space charge, couplings are somewhat noticeable (Figure 18 (c)). When the power-supply noise and the full space-charge effects are included, the transverse couplings are increasingly noticeable. It is thus concluded that the power-supply noise impacting upon a proton beam is dependent upon the strengths of the space-charge defocusing forces in the Booster. What Figure 16 illustrates is the percentage of macroparticles displaced outside of a given average action when the power-supply noise coexists with the full self-fields. The blue markers indicate the fraction of excluded macroparticles at a given emittance at the first tracking turn and the red markers after 1,000 turns. Compared in Figure 17 are the distributions of transverse single-particle actions (J_x and J_y) at the outset of injection and at the 1,000th turn. It becomes ev-

(a) horizontal emittance

(b) vertical emittance

Figure 12 | Growing transverse r.m.s. emittances, starting from the outset of injection through 1,000 tracking turns. When power-supply noise adds to the full space-charge effects, the r.m.s. emittance of proton beams are patently growing without cease.

(a) horizontal plane

(b) vertical plane

Figure 13 | Time evolution of r.m.s. emittances in comparison with actions: (a) horizontal r.m.s. emittance vs. horizontal action; (b) vertical r.m.s. emittance vs. vertical action.

ident that noise-induced beam degradation is escalated as time elapses.

7.2. Coupling Magnitudes

In an ideal system, the normalised r.m.s. emittance remains invariant. However, nonlinear space-charge forces and couplings can induce such processes of degrading beam properties. The increases of the normalised r.m.s. emittances indicate that nonlinear space-charge effects and couplings induced by different types of machine imperfections are existent in the Booster. One of the great advantages of performing accelerator simulations

by tracking huge herds of macroparticles is that one can isolate a system condition to pin down a specific cause of growing emittances under investigation. Therefore, we looked into the transverse couplings by implementing in ORBIT-FERMI new parallel calculations of 4-dimensional transverse emittances (ϵ_{xy}^4) and coupling magnitudes. One can also calculate a squared 2-dimensional r.m.s. emittance on the horizontal plane from the determinant of 2×2 Σ -matrix of beam distributions (Eqn. (24)) and likewise for the counterpart on the vertical plane.

$$\epsilon_{x,rms}^2 = \det \begin{vmatrix} \langle (\Delta x_\beta)^2 \rangle & \langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta p_x \rangle \\ \langle \Delta p_x \Delta x_\beta \rangle & \langle (\Delta p_x)^2 \rangle \end{vmatrix} \quad (27)$$

(a) horizontal plane

(b) vertical plane

Figure 14 | Time evolution of the 2nd moments in transverse planes; the full space-charge forces alone (blue) and stochastic noise and the full space-charge forces combined (red).

(a) horizontal emittance

(b) vertical emittance

Figure 15 | Transverse r.m.s. emittances with reduced intensity; the stochastic noise and space-charge effects combined (red) and the space-charge effects alone (blue). The simulated beam intensity is 6×10^9 protons per RF bucket (ppb) and 5×10^{11} protons in total.

For computing 4-dimensional r.m.s. emittances and couplings, 4-component column matrices ($M_{4,xy}$, $M_{4,yz}$, and $M_{4,xz}$) are defined on the two planes as described in Eqn. (28). By means of generating 4×4 Σ -matrices with the column matrices as in Eqn. (29), one can calculate the determinant of each 4×4 matrix as in Eqns. (30) through (31) that follow:

$$M_{4,xy} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta x_\beta \\ \Delta p_x \\ \Delta y_\beta \\ \Delta p_y \end{bmatrix} \quad M_{4,xz} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta x_\beta \\ \Delta p_x \\ \delta \tilde{E} \\ \Delta \phi \end{bmatrix} \quad M_{4,yz} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta y_\beta \\ \Delta p_y \\ \delta \tilde{E} \\ \Delta \phi \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

$$\begin{cases} \Sigma_{xy} = \Sigma(x_\beta, x'_\beta, y_\beta, y'_\beta) = \langle M_{xy} M_{xy}^T \rangle \\ \Sigma_{xz} = \Sigma(x_\beta, x'_\beta, \delta \tilde{E}, \phi) = \langle M_{xz} M_{xz}^T \rangle \\ \Sigma_{yz} = \Sigma(y_\beta, y'_\beta, \delta \tilde{E}, \phi) = \langle M_{yz} M_{yz}^T \rangle, \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

in which M^T denotes a transpose matrix of M .

$$\epsilon_{xy}^4 = \det \begin{vmatrix} \langle (\Delta x_\beta)^2 \rangle & \langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta p_x \rangle & \langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta y_\beta \rangle & \langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta p_y \rangle \\ \langle \Delta p_x \Delta x_\beta \rangle & \langle (\Delta p_x)^2 \rangle & \langle \Delta p_x \Delta y_\beta \rangle & \langle \Delta p_x \Delta p_y \rangle \\ \langle \Delta y_\beta \Delta x_\beta \rangle & \langle \Delta y_\beta \Delta p_x \rangle & \langle (\Delta y_\beta)^2 \rangle & \langle \Delta y_\beta \Delta p_y \rangle \\ \langle \Delta p_y \Delta x_\beta \rangle & \langle \Delta p_y \Delta p_x \rangle & \langle \Delta p_y \Delta y_\beta \rangle & \langle (\Delta p_y)^2 \rangle \end{vmatrix} \quad (30)$$

Figure 16 | Fractional exclusion of macroparticles at a given average action. The blue indicates fractional rates at the 1st tracking turn and the red indicates at the 1,000th turns. The vertical axis on the left plot is on a linear scale, and the right plot is on a log scale.

Figure 17 | The distribution of actions (J_x and J_y) at the 1st turn and at the 1,000th tracking turns. The O-U noise and 3-D space-charge forces are included. Action distributions at the first turn is indicated in blue, and action distributions at the 1,000th turns in red.

In the same fashion, 4-dimensional emittances and couplings are computed on x - z and y - z planes as well.

$$\epsilon_{xz}^4 = \det \begin{pmatrix} \langle (\Delta x_\beta)^2 \rangle & \langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta p_x \rangle & \langle \Delta x_\beta \delta \tilde{E} \rangle & \langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta \phi \rangle \\ \langle \Delta p_x \Delta x_\beta \rangle & \langle (\Delta p_x)^2 \rangle & \langle \Delta p_x \delta \tilde{E} \rangle & \langle \Delta p_x \Delta \phi \rangle \\ \langle \delta \tilde{E} \Delta x_\beta \rangle & \langle \delta \tilde{E} \Delta p_x \rangle & \langle (\delta \tilde{E})^2 \rangle & \langle \delta \tilde{E} \Delta \phi \rangle \\ \langle \Delta \phi \Delta x_\beta \rangle & \langle \Delta \phi \Delta p_x \rangle & \langle \Delta \phi \delta \tilde{E} \rangle & \langle (\Delta \phi)^2 \rangle \end{pmatrix} \quad (31)$$

$$\epsilon_{yz}^4 = \det \begin{pmatrix} \langle (\Delta y_\beta)^2 \rangle & \langle \Delta y_\beta \Delta p_y \rangle & \langle \Delta y_\beta \delta \tilde{E} \rangle & \langle \Delta y_\beta \Delta \phi \rangle \\ \langle \Delta p_y \Delta y_\beta \rangle & \langle (\Delta p_y)^2 \rangle & \langle \Delta p_y \delta \tilde{E} \rangle & \langle \Delta p_y \Delta \phi \rangle \\ \langle \delta \tilde{E} \Delta y_\beta \rangle & \langle \delta \tilde{E} \Delta p_y \rangle & \langle (\delta \tilde{E})^2 \rangle & \langle \delta \tilde{E} \Delta \phi \rangle \\ \langle \Delta \phi \Delta y_\beta \rangle & \langle \Delta \phi \Delta p_y \rangle & \langle \Delta \phi \delta \tilde{E} \rangle & \langle (\Delta \phi)^2 \rangle \end{pmatrix} \quad (32)$$

Hence, the coupling magnitudes between x - y , y - z , and x - z are calculated thus:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \Delta \epsilon_{xy}^4 &= \left| \epsilon_{xy}^4 - \epsilon_x^2 \cdot \epsilon_y^2 \right| \\ &= \left| \underbrace{\sum C_{xy} (\langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta y_\beta \rangle, \langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta p_y \rangle, \langle \Delta y_\beta \Delta p_x \rangle, \langle \Delta p_x \Delta p_y \rangle)}_{23 \text{ terms}} \right| \\ \Delta \epsilon_{yz}^4 &= \left| \epsilon_{yz}^4 - \epsilon_y^2 \cdot \epsilon_z^2 \right| \\ &= \left| \underbrace{\sum C_{yz} (\langle \Delta y_\beta \delta \tilde{E} \rangle, \langle \Delta y_\beta \Delta \phi \rangle, \langle \delta \tilde{E} \Delta p_y \rangle, \langle \Delta p_y \Delta \phi \rangle)}_{23 \text{ terms}} \right| \\ \Delta \epsilon_{xz}^4 &= \left| \epsilon_{xz}^4 - \epsilon_x^2 \cdot \epsilon_z^2 \right| \\ &= \left| \underbrace{\sum C_{yz} (\langle \Delta x_\beta \delta \tilde{E} \rangle, \langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta \phi \rangle, \langle \delta \tilde{E} \Delta p_x \rangle, \langle \Delta p_x \Delta \phi \rangle)}_{23 \text{ terms}} \right| \end{aligned} \right. \quad (33)$$

where $C_{xy}(\dots)$ denotes coupling terms as a function of $\langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta y_\beta \rangle$, $\langle \Delta x_\beta \Delta p_y \rangle$, $\langle \Delta y_\beta \Delta p_x \rangle$, and $\langle \Delta p_x \Delta p_y \rangle$. Thus, $\Delta \epsilon_{xy}^4$ includes all possible combinations of couplings not only between horizontal and vertical positions, but also between positions and divergence angles in transverse planes. Furthermore, the 4-dimensional couplings can be extended to horizontal and longitudinal planes, and to vertical and longitudinal planes. Figure 18 is an illustration of the 2nd-order cross moment of transverse positions ($\langle \Delta x_r \Delta y_r \rangle$) that enables looking into the transverse couplings in the same vertical scale. In the absence of space charge and the power-supply noise, transverse coupling is not observed. In the presence of space charge, the coupling magnitude is slightly increased, but still marginal. However, with the power-supply noise alone without space charge, the coupling is more noticeable and some perturbations appear over 1,000 turns. When the power-supply noise is coupled to the full space-charge effects, the coupling is boosted. In Figure 19, the turn-by-turn calculations of the cross moments are presented in a form of histogram from which statistics are extracted. The distributions marginally spread out as each type of instability (either space charge, or the power-supply noise) is individually included. When the power-supply noise is applied to macroparticles in the presence of space charge, the r.m.s. value is greater

Figure 18 | Transverse couplings in configuration space

than that of the noise alone by about a factor of two. As derived in Eqn. (33), the coupling between horizontal and longitudinal planes escalates without cease, whilst the power-supply noise coupled to space charge impinges on beams. In Figure 20, progressing from bottom to top, each trace line corresponds to the following cases, respectively: (1) with no space charge, nor the power-supply noise, (2) with the power-supply noise alone, (3) with space charge alone, (4) with the power-supply noise co-existing with the 3-D space-charge forces. It is evident in the Figure 20 that transverse coupling is synergistically amplified when the power-supply noise is coupled to the full space-charge forces, when compared to the other cases. From the calculations of the coupling strengths, $\Delta\epsilon_{xy}$ and $\langle \Delta x_r \Delta y_r \rangle$, consistent results were obtained thus: When space-charge forces are coupled with power-supply ripples their impacts on proton beams

can be intensified at resonance frequencies.

7.3. Beam-Halo Formation

The computation scheme of maximum extent of the coordinates of displaced macroparticles inside a round beam at each tracking turn is implemented in the noise module. Eqn. (34) includes only physical coordinates (x and y) of a maximum-displaced macroparticle at the location of a random noise node [2]. It is referred to as the *halo magnitude* $R_{H,2}$:

$$R_{H,2} = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} \Big|_{max} \quad (34)$$

The *halo magnitude* in 4 dimensions $R_{H,4}$, which includes both horizontal and vertical positions and angles of a maximum-

Figure 19 | Distributions of the magnitude of the 2nd-order cross-moment ($\langle xy \rangle$).

Figure 20 | Time evolution of 4-dimensional coupling strength $\Delta\epsilon_{xy}^4$. Its vertical axis is in units of π -mm-mrad².

displaced particle, is given in Eqn. (35):

$$R_{H,4} = \left(x / \sqrt{\beta_x} \right)^2 + \left(\sqrt{\beta_x} \cdot x' \right)^2 + \left(y / \sqrt{\beta_y} \right)^2 + \left(\sqrt{\beta_y} \cdot y' \right)^2 \Big|_{max}, \quad (35)$$

where β_x and β_y are optics functions at the location of one noise node. Calculating two types of the halo magnitudes ($R_{H,2}$ and $R_{H,4}$) yields consistent results. As Figure 21 illustrates, the evolution of the halo magnitudes is represented in green and smoothed data is in blue. Due to large oscillatory behaviour of the halo magnitudes, the data points were smoothed. The smoothed curve in Figure 22 shows with clarity a growing pattern of maximum-displaced macroparticles from the physical centre of magnet's aperture.

Figure 21 | Halo magnitudes R_{max} with the power-supply noise in the presence of the full space-charge forces; the blue trace in the background indicates a smoothed curve with the spline function.

Figure 22 | Halo magnitudes R_{max} in the presence of the power-supply noise along with the full space-charge forces (red) in contrast to the full space-charge forces alone (blue).

8. CLOSING REMARKS AND OUTLOOK

Based upon the measured current ripples from the power supplies, the elaborate and realistic noise model was constructed by tuning up in search of stochastic parameters. A set of the three parameters (*time step*, *autocorrelation time*, and *noise strength*) empowered characterising the power-supply noise under investigation. Consequently, the FFT power-spectral densities between the measured ripples and simulated noise were closely matched. Leveraging the technique of parallel computing for enhanced accuracy enabled incorporating and tracking a sufficiently large number of macroparticles with full space-charge calculations in a practical amount of computing time. As found with careful diagnosis, the existent common-mode voltages at each power supply are the principal culprit that triggers the rip-

ple currents.

The foregoing results obtained from simulating and tracking beams make evident that frequency-dependent noise originating from the power supplies, when coupled with space-charge effects, leads to decidedly heightened beam-degrading process—*i.e.*, emittance growth, beam-halo formation, particle losses, and radiation damage—at the low injection energy of the Booster.

Our investigations evidenced that the adverse effects of power-supply’s minute ripples are dependent upon the strength of space charge. Hence, we are proposing two viable approaches to de-escalate the process of beam losses and radiation damage resulting from coexisting fluctuational currents and space charge. The first is to debilitate inherent space-charge forces themselves. Operating a dual radio-frequency (RF) system with a proper choice of RF parameters can further reduce space-charge effects in high-intensity proton machines by manoeuvring charge distributions in longitudinal space [11]. Consequently, one can suppress the resultant phenomena of degrading beam properties. The second is to devise instrumental techniques to counterbalance common-mode-conducted EMI originating from the power supplies.

According to the equivalent-circuit model, it is worth pursuing experimental measurements, or detection of harmful high-frequency resonances existent in the magnet system (Figure 11). Once confirmed, a cluster of parasitic resonances are making its presence experienced all around the Booster ring during operation. It is, therefore, essential to damp out those offending resonances, such that their adverse influences on beams can be counteracted and insulated from amplifying.

Upon injecting even more realistic, or *nonuniform* charge-density distributions, the effects of space charge increases, so does the damaging influence of minute current fluctuations on the beams. Given the current outlook, the methodology of modelling the noise-induced effects on beams is expected to be well applicable to other synchrotrons, or storage rings, in which the space-charge effects are of main concern. This conclusion is a clear implication that power-supply ripples can induce more prominent development of beam-degrading process in low- γ storage rings of intensity frontier over a longer period of beam circulation.

- [1] Bohn, C. L. & Sideris, I. V., *Fluctuations Do Matter: Large Noise-Enhanced Halos in Charged-Particle Beams*. Phys. Rev. Lett., **91**, 26, (2003).
- [2] Bohn, C. L., *Collective Modes and Colored Noise as Beam Halo Amplifiers*. AIP Conf. Proc., **737**, 456–461, (2004).
- [3] Fermilab’s Booster home page, <http://www-ad.fnal.gov/proton/booster>.
- [4] Aguilar-Arevalo, A. A. et al., *Significant Excess of Electronlike Events in the MiniBooNE Short-Baseline Neutrino Experiment*. PRL **121**, 221801 (2018).
- [5] Abratenko, P. et al., *First Measurements of Inclusive Muon Neutrino Charged Current Differential Cross Sections on Argon at $E_\nu \sim 0.8$ GeV with the MicroBooNE Detector*. PRL **123**, 131801 (2019).
- [6] Galambos, J., *ORBIT—A Ring Injection Code With Space Charge*. Proc. of Particle Accelerator Conference, New York, USA, (1999).
- [7] Box, G. E. P. & Muller, M. E., *A Note on the Generation of Random Normal Deviates*, Annals. Math. Stat., **29**, 2, 1958, pp. 610–611.
- [8] Uhlenbeck, G. E. & Ornstein, L. S., *ON THE THEORY OF THE BROWNIAN MOTION*. Phys. Rev., **36**, 823, (1930).
- [9] Van Kampen, N. G., *Stochastic Processes in Physics and Chemistry*. (North-Holland, 1992).
- [10] Holmes, J. A. et al., *ORBIT: Beam Dynamics Calculations for High-Intensity Rings*. Proc. of European Particle Accelerator Conference., Paris, France, (2002).
- [11] Yoon, P. S., Johnson, D. E., & Chou, W. *The Modeling of Microbunch Injection into the Main Injector* arXiv:0802.2430v1 [physics.acc-ph],(2008).
- [12] Mohan, N., Undeland, T., & Robbins, R. *Power Electronics*, John Wiley & Sons, 500–501, (1989).
- [13] Horowitz, P. & Hill, W. *The Art of Electronics*, Cambridge University Press, (1989).
- [14] Einstein, A. & Hopf, L. *Statistische Untersuchung der Bewegung eines Resonators in einem Strahlungsfeld*, Ann. d. Phys. (Leipzig), **33**, 1105, (1910).
- [15] Einstein, A. & Fürth, R. H. Ed. *Investigations on the Theory of Brownian Movement*, Methuen, London, 1926, Dover Publication, New York, (1956).
- [16] Langevin, P. *Sur la Théorie du motion de brownien*, Comptes Rendus Acad. Sci. (Paris), **146**, pp. 530–533, (1908).
- [17] Jannesai, M. et al. *A Langevin equation that governs the irregular stick-slip nano-scale friction*, Sci. Rep. (2019) 9:12505.
- [18] Taylor, G. I. *Proc. London Math. Soc.* **22**, 196 (1920).
- [19] Doob, J. L. *The Brownian Movement and Stochastic Equation*, Annals of Mathematics, **43**, 2, pp. 351–369, (1942).
- [20] Wang, M. G. & Uhlenbeck, G. E. *On the Theory of the Brownian Motion II*, Rev. Mod. Phys. **17**, 2–3, pp. 323–342, (1945).
- [21] Press, W. H., Flannery, B. P. & Teukolsky, S. A. *Numerical Recipes in C++*, (Cambridge University, Cambridge, 1998), pp. 292–293.
- [22] Courtesy of M. Kufer and S. Fang of Fermilab Accelerator Division Electrical Engineering Department
- [23] Engelbert, J., Nguyen, T. & Thurston, C. *B2 Spice A/D Version 4 User’s Manual*, Beige Bag Software, Inc., (2002).
- [24] Galambos, J. et al., *Comparison of Simulated and Observed Beam Profile Broadening in the Proton Storage Ring and the Role of Space Charge*, PRST-AB, **3**, 034201, (2000).
- [25] Flöttmann, K. *Some basic features of the beam emittance*, PRST-AB, **6**, 034202 (2003).
- [26] MAD 8 home page: <http://hansg.home.cern.ch/hansg/mad/mad8/mad8.html>
- [27] Reiser, M. *Theory of Charged Particle Beams*, Wiley & Sons, (1994).
- [28] Gardiner, W. *Handbook of Stochastic Processes*, Springer-Verlag, (2004).
- [29] Stratonovich, R. L. *Introduction to the Theory of Random Noise, Vol. I and II*, Gordon and Breach, New York (1963).
- [30] Struckmeier, J. *Stochastic effects in real and simulated charged particle beams*, PRST-AB, **13**, (2010).